
**MEDIA ADVOCACY FOR CONDOM USE AMONG SEXUALLY
ACTIVE POPULATIONS AS A MEANS TO COMBAT NEW
INFECTIONS OF HIV/AIDS IN AKWA IBOM STATE**

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the use of media advocacy and behaviour change communication to promote condom use among sexually active populations in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, as a means to combat new HIV/AIDS infections. The key objectives are to address the lack of HIV/AIDS messages in contemporary media and encourage safer reproductive practices, especially condom use among vulnerable groups. Grounded in the Health Benefit Model and World Bank Intervention Cycle framework, the paper puts forward a comprehensive communication plan leveraging mass media, social media, conferences, body art, and celebrity endorsements to convey tailored messages countering myths around condom use and building self-efficacy. The activities aim to increase visibility, stimulate engagement, measure feedback, and ultimately reduce HIV transmission by promoting consistent condom use. The impact will be evaluated through program logs and condoms distributed, with the overarching goal being a decrease in new infections across Akwa Ibom. If effective, the model can be adopted nationally. The paper concludes that strategic communication efforts are imperative to improving reproductive health outcomes and mitigating Nigeria's HIV/AIDS epidemic.

**Keywords: Media Advocacy, Behaviour Change Communication,
HIV/AIDS, Condom Use, Akwa Ibom**

Introduction

Background of the Study

Good health is a key index of societal development. The international community emphasizes that it has enshrined as a third cardinal goal that every community that should be called developed should achieve “good health and wellbeing” amongst 16 other conditions. These conditions, the United Nations (2015) hopes it is achievable in 2030. For there to be any meaningful development, the actors involved must be healthy and in sound mind.

However, the plaguing Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and the resultant syndrome AIDS has left many African countries almost bereft of hope at attaining the 2030 mark. Nigeria as a country is not left out of this seeming continental condition. The last concluded national AIDS indicator impact survey (NAIIS, 2019) revealed that the national prevalence of HIV is 1.4% (of the total recorded cases worldwide) with an estimated 1.9 million people infected with the virus.

The continual rise in the rate of new infections in Nigeria has come as a defeatist statement for the National HIV and AIDS Strategic Plan 2017-2021, developed by the National Agency for the Control of Aids (NACA). This plan's first thematic area of focus was for the “Prevention of HIV among General and Key Populations;” with a focus to “significantly reduce the incidences of new HIV infections by 2021.” This they hoped to achieve through “strategic behaviour change communication for general, key and vulnerable populations;” amongst other things. This strategic plan was reviewed in 2019 but it was still aimed at supporting a national AIDS response by urgently communicating the most essential new findings and providing renewed strategic guidance. Simply put, the new plan aimed to improve HIV/AIDS communication as a means to combat an unfavourable statistics that Nigeria kept recording new cases of infection after it identified low dissemination of information about HIV, especially in rural areas as one major cause of the rise in new infections.

Akwa Ibom tops that chart of states with 5.6% prevalence rate with over 181,000 people living with the virus (NACA 2021). And this data, many health workers argue are only from the tested and confirmed cases, positing that more cases may be revealed if more persons come out to get tested. Akwa Ibom

AIDS Indicator Survey shows that a number of factors are responsible for the increase in infection in Akwa Ibom State; one of such is lack of HIV/AIDS Education (Adedokun *et al.*, 2020). This made Badru *et al.* (2020) to opine that there should be an increase in awareness for the most vulnerable population (14-25) as a means to reduce infection.

Although HIV/AIDS messages initially flooded the Nigerian media air space in the early 2000s, but a study by Obono (2011) revealed a disturbing and unfavourable decline of HIV/AIDS content in contemporary media. This begets the question - are the days of HIV/AIDS messages/contents in contemporary media over? Bearing in mind that there are other young adults who in the 2000s were not yet born, or were children who may not have grasped the severity of the HIV/AIDS pandemic as at that time it was initially aired.

Another major challenge is that going by the active population that the Akwa Ibom HIV/AIDS Survey revealed as the most vulnerable, how can one use communication action to engender safer reproductive change among sexually active populations? These are the concerns that this paper hopes to address using the World Bank Intervention Cycle development model that was developed in 2015. The objective is to show how communication action can be targeted to reach the vulnerable population in the hope that the right messages can lead to the adoption of safer reproductive practices, especially using condoms as a measure to reduce the risk of increased new HIV infections.

Nigeria's HIV/AIDS Epidemic

The first case of AIDS was reported in Nigeria in 1986. Since then, the epidemic has grown from a concentrated epidemic experienced by high-risk groups, to a generalized epidemic. Prevalence rate differ from state to state, but Akwa Ibom State has the highest prevalence rate pegged at 5.8%.

In Nigeria, the major route of transmission of HIV is through unprotected sexual intercourse. Studies among risk populations show that heterosexual sex makes up about 80%. Mother-to-child transmission of HIV (which has been argued by some to be an outcome of heterosexual relationships) and transfusion of infected blood and blood products on the other hand, account for the other notable modes of transmission (NACA, 2015). Risk factors and drivers of the HIV epidemic in Nigeria include early sexual debut, low condom

use, transactional sex and multiple sexual partners, low perception of risk, transfusion of poorly screened blood, poor injection safety, etc. (FMoH, 2010). These peculiarities of HIV transmission make HIV a serious public health issue. This threat is further compounded by the poor state of Nigeria's health system, failed leadership, persisting economic hardship, general poverty, crumbling education system, lack of reliable surveillance and disease control system structure, amongst other things.

Mitigating HIV/AIDS in Nigeria

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA) had far back in 2015 identified what the country must do to end Human Immuno-deficiency Virus (HIV)/Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) by 2030. 2030 is a very significant year as the world development index has enshrined in the Sustainable Development Goals will also be strategically reviewed in the same year.

Then Director General of NACA, Prof. John Idoko, at a press conference in Abuja, to mark the World AIDS Day on December 1, 2015, identified among other things: Increase domestic funding to achieve a fully funded AIDS response at all levels; fully operationalize 90-90-90 strategy to eliminate progression to AIDS, premature deaths and HIV transmission; ensure combination prevention for all populations; expand HIV Counseling and Testing (HCT), Antiretroviral treatment (ART) and Prevention of Mother to Child Transmission (PMTCT) services; pursue a policy of local manufacture of essential commodities (antiretroviral drugs, test kits and condoms); and address barriers to accessing HIV and AIDS prevention and treatment services (Idoko, 2015).

The 90-90-90 strategy of the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS is an ambitious treatment target to help end the AIDS epidemic. This ambitious but achievable target demands that:

- a. By 2020, 90% of all people living with HIV will know their HIV status.
- b. By 2020, 90% of all people with diagnosed HIV infection will receive sustained antiretroviral therapy.
- c. 2020, 90% of all people receiving antiretroviral therapy will have viral suppression. (UNAIDS, 2014)

For Nigeria, these targets were not achievable at the end of the 2020-year mark, however, some progress were recorded. It is recorded that more than 279 000 people living with HIV got HIV treatment in 2020, improvement in viral load coverage and suppression, and there was increased assess to HIV counselling and testing. The UNAIDS indicator rates Nigeria performance thus:

“At the end of 2020, progress on the 90–90–90 treatment targets were 73–89–78—that is, 73% of people living with HIV had been diagnosed, 89% of those diagnosed were accessing treatment and 78% of those accessing treatment were virally suppressed. (UNAIDS, 2021)

On this performance report, UNAIDS is of the opinion that Nigeria is ready to begin the next strategic phase of HIV mitigation that targets 95-95-95 by 2030. This, they hope to combine with reducing new infections world over to 200,000 persons or lower, and ensuring communities with zero discrimination for people living with HIV.

HIV response in Nigeria has been donor driven with government playing mostly the coordinating role. For instance, in 2016, the US President Emergency Funds for AIDS Relief (PEPFAR) planned funding for HIV response in Nigeria stood at \$235million. PEPFAR and the U.S. Agency for International Development (USAID) introduced Reaching Impact, Saturation and Epidemic Control (RISE) project. RISE is to help address the challenges of HIV/AIDS in Nigeria and to reduce the burden of unmet needs across states, the project in Nigeria is expected to be a wrap in 2024. A notable impact of the RISE project is the U=U Campaign that was introduced in 2017 is that the campaign advocates that early diagnose and treatment of HIV/AIDS can lead to a reduction in viral load till it becomes undetectable, and when HIV becomes undetectable in the blood stream it becomes not transmittable.

In Akwa Ibom, there are some NGOs who are implementing funded HIV/AIDS intervention programmes, and many of them are championing the cause of reducing new infections in Akwa Ibom communities through various advocacies. How well this advocacy has worked is in contention as there seem to be no significant drop in the rate of new infections.

Behaviour Change Communication

Behaviour Change Communication also dubbed communication for development are targeted strategies and processes that engages communication activities as a means to influencing individuals or groups of individuals to embrace some set of positive predetermined behaviours that will lead to social change and development (Adhikari, 2019).

Mark Lund, the former director for UK's Central Office for Information noted this in the foreword:

Tackling some of society's most intractable and costly problems most often requires us to change behaviours in some way... Government has a number of tools at its disposal to stimulate behaviour change, from legislation, regulation and taxation to providing information, persuasion, engagement and working in partnership. In most cases, putting these tools into action will require communications in some form. (*Communications and Behaviour Change, 2015*).

BCC comes into effect when there is a noticeable tilt towards negative, undesirable or deviant behaviour, and at other times, it comes into play when there is a need for a paradigm shift in the status quo for the better. An understanding of behavioural modes and how people communicate and perceive phenomena around them is equally important. Packard of fhi360 notes that for BCC to be successful, it must be “interactive, theory based, and research driven communication processes and strategies for change at the individual, community, and social levels.”

Many health and development programs use BCC to motivate people to adopt and sustain healthy behaviours and lifestyles (JHU, 2008). However, behaviour change cannot happen overnight, this is due to a lot of interlocutions between interpersonal or environmental factors surrounding people (Ngigi and Busola, 2018). Sustaining healthy behaviour usually requires a continuing investment in BCC as part of an overall health program. Sometimes, the enactment and reinforcement may be needed to drive home a message, making sure people can retain and recall, which in turn will deepen interpretation and lead to subsequent behaviour change.

BCC tool kit includes strategies like body art, billboards, posters, mass media (electronic and print), social media, town halls, social marketing, public service advertising, feedback forums, peer play groups, advocacy tour, theatre, extension workers and opinion leadership. There is no one strategy that can deliver on all the benefits that BCC has to offer, sometimes, there is crisscross of tools used; the future of behaviour change and health promotion is through the application of a comprehensive strategy to better enable people to have a healthy lifestyle (Laverack, 2017).

Odimegwu *et al.* (2017) notes that it is necessary to intensify advocacy and awareness to change people's orientation if HIV/AIDS is to be combatted, especially the war against stigma and discrimination. Similarly, states have been advised on the need to strategically position and scale-up outreach and service programmes, not just on the dangers of HIV, but also to effectively combat stigma and discrimination if Nigeria aims to have a fully successful HIV response. This they can do by sharing the burden of communication for change to the key population by engaging community-based organizations (Lo *et al.*, 2021).

Theoretical Framework

This work will be rooted in the Health Benefit Model, and The World Bank Intervention Cycle Model.

The Health Benefit Model

The health benefit model was propounded by some social scientists in the US Public Health Service in the early 1950s to understand why people refused to adopt disease diagnosis and prevention strategies for the detection, management and prevention of diseases. The model was derived from the psychological and behavioural theory with the foundation of health-related behaviour of the desire to avoid illnesses and the belief that a specific health action will prevent or cure illnesses.

Overall, a person's response depends largely on his/her perception of the merits and demerits related to health behaviour. The HBM takes root on some constructs listed as follows:

- a. Perceived Susceptibility
- b. Perceived Severity
- c. Perceived Benefits

- d. Perceived Barriers
- e. Cue to Action
- f. Self-Efficacy (sphweb.bumc.bu.edu, 2022).

The World Bank Intervention Cycle Model

The World Bank Intervention Cycle Model was proposed in 2015. This model recognizes that individuals think automatically, think socially; and as such, policy makers need to improve the intervention cycle and development effectiveness. While it concentrates more on the “definition and diagnosis of problems and expending more cognitive and financial investments at that stage, it can also lead to better-designed interventions” (World Bank 2015, p.192). The model among other things suggests a combination of methods, testing of processes to achieve at a given goal. The model posits that intervention should be holistic and sustainable. That even after project timelines, more redefinition can be added to improve future plans.

The components of this model include definition and diagnosis, design, implementation and evaluation, adoption and adaptation, redefinition and re-diagnosis (if needed).

Definition and Diagnosis

Attempting a definition of the problem, there is a deficit of HIV/AIDS messages on mainstream and social media. Plurality has made media very personal and as such, people tend to avoid the conversation about their reproductive health, especially HIV/AIDS. Only very few persons in the sexually active bracket practice abstinence. The HIV survey of 2017 had already established that about 80% of new infections are due to unprotected

sexual intercourse. Sadly, there are very few people who are practicing mutual exclusivity; this is to say there are a lot people with multiple sexual relationships, especially people who move from one relationship to another.

This problem is compounded by the fact that unprotected sex has been seen as a test of trust in many relationships, this should not be so. On the other hand, there is also a growing mediated sex work called hookups. So, people are having commercial sex without having to declare their status as one or open shop. There is also a flourishing community of sexual orientations, especially the gays and lesbians. Sadly, there is apathy towards purchasing and using condoms by many sexually active individuals.

Understanding that one cannot will it away that people should stop having sex; however, one can encourage people to take charge of their lives by using condoms. There is an observed apathy to the use of condoms due to familiarity with sexual partner, perceived reduction in sexual pleasure and a total denial to the fact that HIV/AIDS is real (Oranu *et al.*, 2020; Usman *et al.*, 2017; and Ajayi *et al.*, 2019). Focus here will be to address people who have unprotected sex due to three reasons: those who use it as a test of trust, those who say condoms deny them pleasure and lastly, those who think condoms are costly.

Design

To design a campaign that will address this, this is the message map designed for it.

Message Map

Category: People who have unprotected sex as a test of trust	Category: People who have unprotected sex because to them condoms reduce sexual pleasure	Category: People who have unprotected sex because they cannot afford condoms
Key Message/Fact 1 Unprotected sex is not a test of trust.	Key Message/Fact 2 Condoms do not reduce sexual enjoyment.	Key Message/Fact 3 Condoms are cheap compared to the cost of treating diseases.
Supporting Fact 1-1 Using a condom is to promote health safe sex.	Supporting Fact 2-1 Condoms are made from a variety of natural and artificial latex that does not impede sexual pleasure.	Supporting Fact 3-1 There are free condoms given at many heart-to-heart health facilities near you.

Supporting Fact 1-2 Using condoms can even build confidence among partners.	Supporting Fact 2-2 There are condom types for men and for women, as well as condoms of different sizes and from different manufacturers.	Supporting Fact 3-2 Condom use correctly and consistently reduces your chances of getting HIV/AIDS through sex.
Supporting Fact 1-3 You need not worry about other STIs and even pregnancy, when you use a condom.	Supporting Fact 2-3 Discuss with your partner his/her preference of condom.	Supporting Fact 3-3 Partners can chip in to buy condoms they can both use.
Tagline or slogan 1-1 Condoms are safe	Tagline or slogan 2-1 Condoms feel good	Tagline or slogan 3-1 Condoms are reliable

Adapted from Johns (2013)

Implementation

To address these messages, the following communication plan shall be used:

Communication Implementation Plan

ACTIVITY	OBJECTIVE	MEDIA	FREQUENCY	AUDIENCE	EXPECTED OUTCOME
Jingles and announcements	Intimate the public on the need to use condoms for protection against HI/AIDS.	Radio, TV, Newspaper	Daily for 2 years	General	Increase awareness against HIV/AIDS
Website and Social Media Interaction	To open interactions with vulnerable populations where they can access help	Website, emails, Facebook, Whatsapp, Instagram, snapchat, Pinterest and other platforms	Daily for 2 years	All publics and stakeholders	Increased awareness and visibility, stimulate engagement on a variety of topic of interest to the public and stakeholders, and to gauge feedback

Production of Monthly HIV/AIDS Watch report	To acknowledge work done, and the contributions of partners. To engage community and stakeholder groups. To provide a yardstick to measure program	Magazine and e-book publishing, emails	Monthly	All stakeholder groups and the publics (especially project partners)	Increased accountability and transparency, cultivate more strategic partnerships to fight HIV, cultivate and inculcate community ownership and participation
Thematic Conferences and Symposia	Raise advocacy for condom use areas among key population.	Mass group conference	As needed	All publics and stakeholders	Increase awareness and visibility. It will also build confidence to talk about condom use among population
Production of body arts and other outdoor infomercials	Increase visibility, stimulate engagement among population, serve as souvenir	Face caps, T – shirts, Fliers and Billboards	As needed	All publics	Increase visibility and awareness
Social Media Challenge	To stimulate engagement from the public and to measure feedback	Social media (Facebook, twitter, Instagram)	As needed	All publics	Increase awareness and traction of program impact
Celebrity Endorsement and Involvement	To stimulate community engagement, increase awareness and campaign adoption, create impact in communities using popular factors and actors	Face-to-face Social media (celebrities in mind are Tuface Idibia - popular Nigerian Muisician. Trust Ekong – Nigerian super eagles soccer player. And Eve Esin – popular Nigerian actress)	As needed	General	Increased awareness, endorsement and participation to widely boost public acceptance

Advocacy Tour	Communicate better with government, parents and other players about HIV/AIDS projects. Advocate the inclusion of sex education in school curriculum	Face-to-face	As needed	Ministry of education. Ministry of health, SACA	Government partners with private sector to achieve inclusion of sex education in school curriculum
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The evaluation of this programme will be done using programme logs and unit of artifacts produced. However, if this increases the number of distributed condoms among population, it will be that the programme has recorded some successes. If this leads ultimately to a reduction in new infections across the state, then this campaign has been very effective.

If this proved to be effective, it can be adopted or adapted for a national response to reduce HIV/AIDS.

Conclusion

There is need for HIV/AIDS development workers in Akwa Ibom state to re-strategize in order to deliver a better communication engagement plan for the state if there is seriousness to address the widening gyre of new infections every day. If tenets of this model are employed, Akwa Ibom state will have a better reproductive health communication experience that will lead to behaviour change and subsequently reduce HIV/AIDS infections.

References

- Adedokun O, Badru T, Khamofu H, Negedu-Momoh OR, Iwara E, Agbakwuru C, et al. (2020). Akwa Ibom AIDS indicator survey: Key findings and lessons learnt. PLoS ONE 15(6): e0234079. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234079>
- Adhikari S. (2019). Behavior Change Communication (BCC): Importance and Strategies. Retrieved from <https://www.publichealthnotes.com/1142-2/#:~:text=Importance%20of%20BCC%3A&text=BCC%20helps%20to%20trigger%20and, strategies%20are%20efficient%20and%20effective.>

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References

- Adedokun O, Badru T, Khamofu H, Negedu-Momoh OR, Iwara E, Agbakwuru C, et al. (2020). Akwa Ibom AIDS indicator survey: Key findings and lessons learnt. PLoS ONE 15(6): e0234079. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234079>
- Adhikari S. (2019). Behavior Change Communication (BCC): Importance and Strategies. Retrieved from <https://www.publichealthnotes.com/1142-2/#:~:text=Importance%20of%20BCC%3A&text=BCC%20helps%20to%20trigger%20and, strategies%20are%20efficient%20and%20effective>.
- Ajayi, A.I., Ismail, K.O. & Akpan, W. Factors associated with consistent condom use: a cross-sectional survey of two Nigerian universities. BMC Public Health 19, 1207 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7543-1>
- Badru, T.; Mwaisak J.; Khamofu, H.; Agbakwuru, C.; Adedokun, O.; Pandey, SR.; Essiet, P.; James, E.; Chen-Carrington, A.; Mastro, TD.; Aliyu, SA.; & Torpey, K. (2020). HIV comprehensive knowledge and prevalence among young adolescents in Nigeria: evidence from Akwa Ibom AIDS indicator survey, 2017. BMC Public Health.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-019-7890-y>

- Federal Ministry of Health, FMOH (2010) National HIV/Syphilis Sentinel Survey Report.
- Idoko J. (2015). “what Nigeria should do to end HIV by 2030” text of a press briefing to commemorate the 2015 World AIDS Day, Abuja
- John Hopkins University Center for Communication Programs (2008). Tools for Behaviour Change Communication. Published with support from USAID
- John, M. (2013). The Power of Coordinated Campaign Effort and Communicating Key Messages. Retrieved from http://www.keepitsacred.org/network/files/Communicating_Key_Messages_Webinar_NNN_3_26_13a.pdf on January 3, 2022
- Lo J, Nwafor SU, Schwitters AM, Mitchell A, Sebastian V, Stafford KA, Ezirim I, Charurat M, McIntyre AF (2021). Key Population Hotspots in Nigeria for Targeted HIV Program Planning: Mapping, Validation, and Reconciliation. *JMIR Public Health Surveill* 7(2)
- National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA), 2015 Global AIDS Response Country Progress Report Nigeria GARCPR 2015 (pp.4)
- Ngigi, S. & Busolo, D. (2018). Behaviour Change Communication in Health Promotion: Appropriate Practices and Promising Approaches. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*. 7.
- Ngigi, S. & Busolo, D. (2018). Behaviour Change Communication in Health Promotion: Appropriate Practices and Promising Approaches. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*. 7. 10.24940/ijird/2018/v7/i9/SEP18027.
- Obono, K. (2011). Media Strategies of HIV/AIDS Communication for Behaviour Change in South West Nigeria. *Journal Africana*.

Odey, J.E. (2004). The role of the family in sex and sexuality education. The Journal of family development, 1: 77-85

Odimegwu, C., Akinyemi, J & Alabi, O. (2017). "HIV-Stigma in Nigeria: Review of Research Studies, Policies, and Programmes", AIDS Research and Treatment, vol. 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/5812650>

Oranu, E. , Woruka, P. and Nonye-Enyindah, E. (2020) Evaluation of Condom Use among University Undergraduates in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Journal of Biosciences and Medicines, 8, 31-41.

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS, NACA (2017). National HIV and AIDS Strategic plan 2017-2021

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS, NACA (2019) Nigeria HIV/AIDS Indicator and Impact Survey, NAIIS.

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS, NACA (2019). Revised National HIV and AIDS Strategic Framework 2019-2021: Future Directions for the HIV/AIDS Response in Nigeria

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS, NACA (2021) Nigeria Prevalence Rate. Retrieved from <https://naca.gov.ng/nigeria-prevalence-rate/> on May 5, 2021

The National Agency for the Control of AIDS, NACA (2021). Nigeria Prevalence Rate. Retrieved from <https://naca.gov.ng/nigeria-prevalence-rate/> on May 5, 2021

The United Nations (2015) The 17 Goals. Retrieved from <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> on May 5, 2021

UNAIDS (2014). 90-90-90: An ambitious treatment target to help end the AIDS epidemic. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS).

UNAIDS (2015) Understanding Fast-track: accelerating action to end AIDS